

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF SOME SURFACE AND GROUND WATER QUALITY PARAMETERS FOR AQUACULTURE WITHIN JIMETA METROPOLIS OF ADAMAWA STATE

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Abstract

A comparative analysis of some surface and groundwater physico-chemical parameters was studied over three months. Water samples were taken from Lake Geriyo, River Benue, Well, and Borehole twice a week. The water quality parameters measured were temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, transparency, electrical conductivity, total dissolved solids, biological oxygen demand (BOD), and free carbon dioxide. The highest mean temperature was observed from well water ($30.83 \pm 1.63^\circ\text{C}$) while the lowest was from Upper River Benue ($27 \pm 2.11^\circ\text{C}$). The mean pH values were 6.92 ± 0.32 , 7.01 ± 0.41 , 6.04 ± 0.24 and 6.39 ± 0.15 for Lake Geriyo, Upper River Benue, well water and borehole respectively and there was no significant difference in their pH values. The highest mean dissolved oxygen was observed in the Upper Benue River (6.27 ± 1.79 mg/l) while Lake Geriyo, well water and borehole water had 4.23 ± 1.32 mg/l, 3.8 ± 1.08 mg/l and 3.67 ± 1.53 mg/l respectively. The electrical conductivity was very high in borehole water with a mean value of 668.33 ± 2.11 ppm while Lake Geriyo, Upper Benue River and well water had lower electrical conductivity values of 230.33 ± 3.45 ppm, 71.5 ± 1051 ppm and 200 ± 2.28 ppm respectively. Also, the total dissolved solids were very high in borehole water (307.5 ± 2.64 ppm) compared to what was obtained in lake Geriyo (107.5 ± 2.23 ppm), Upper Benue River (39.17 ± 1.84 ppm) and well water (83.12 ± 1.68 ppm). The biochemical oxygen demand was higher in the Upper Benue River (4.32 ± 0.38 mg/l) compared to that of Lake Geriyo (2.71 ± 0.54 mg/l), well water (1.11 ± 0.21 mg/l) and borehole water (1.89 ± 0.51 mg/l). However, all measured water quality parameters are within the acceptable ranges of international and national standards for domestic waters. Hence, the water can be classified as good, stable and healthy for aquaculture purposes.

Keywords: Water Quality Parameters, Surface Water, Groundwater, Jimeta Metropolis, Borehole Water

Introduction

Water is a vital element in all aspects of life and plays an extremely important role in the continuous existence of human beings and the ecosystem as a whole. Water is important for aquatic organisms including fish, for their survival, growth, recreation, nutrition, and reproduction. Currently, water is considered an emergency resource due to the negative effects of climate change, rapid population growth, urbanization, inappropriate use, and unsustainable management in many countries all over the world (IPCC, 2007). Numerous complex factors, such as population growth and urbanisation, seawater intrusion, improper wastewater treatment, overexploitation, and unsustainable management, frequently have an impact on water resources in coastal regions (Ridolfi, 2011).

Lake Geriyo and River Benue, as surface water have been used for so many purposes such as fishing, irrigation activities (farming), transportation, and even for domestic uses, especially for the communities along the watercourse. Communities also depend on well and borehole waters as a source of water for their daily activities such as domestic usage and fish farming (aquaculture). Naturally, water resources interact frequently together (Shaw, 2013), such that if one of them is polluted or affected, it may be a threat to another. In order to use and manage water resources sustainably, it is necessary to consider not only surface water but also groundwater source as an important component of the water cycle. Therefore, understanding the physical and chemical characteristics of surface water and groundwater is fundamental to the development of sustainable water resources management and policies most especially for aquacultural purposes. Furthermore, the quality of surface water and groundwater can directly impact the health and productivity of aquatic ecosystems. Proper management and monitoring of these water sources are crucial to ensuring the success and sustainability of aquaculture practices. Additionally, implementing effective pollution control measures and promoting responsible water usage can help mitigate the potential risks associated with farming (aquaculture) activities on water resources

Materials and Methods

Study Areas

The surface waters which are Lake Geriyo and Upper Benue River lie between longitude 12°25`E and latitude 9°8`N and longitude 12°47`E and latitude 9°28`N respectively of Adamawa State. Lake Geriyo is a floodplain lake directly adjacent to the Upper Benue River. The borehole and well waters serve as the groundwater and they are within the Jimeta metropolis of Adamawa State.

Sample Collection

A total of 10 boreholes and 10 wells were randomly selected within the sample area. Water samples were collected from the groundwater source and the surface water source twice a week and in triplicate for a period of three months (January to March). Pre-cleaned and labeled glass bottles were used to collect water samples. Parameters such as temperature, conductivity, hydrogen ion concentration (pH), Dissolved Oxygen, Total Dissolved Solid, and transparency were determined in situ, while free carbon dioxide and Biological oxygen demand (BOD) were determined in the laboratory following the standard procedure of APHA (1998). Samples were usually collected between 8.00 a.m. and 9.00 a.m.

Figure 1: Map of lake Geriyo.

Results

The results showed that well water had the highest mean temperature ($30.83 \pm 1.63^\circ\text{C}$) while the Upper River Benue had the lowest mean temperature ($27.12 \pm 2.11^\circ\text{C}$) as shown in Table 1. The Upper Benue River had the highest mean pH value of 7.01 ± 0.41 while Lake Geriyo, well water, and borehole water had 6.92 ± 0.32 , 6.04 ± 0.24 and 6.39 ± 0.15 respectively. The mean dissolved oxygen was found to be highest in the Upper River Benue (6.27 ± 1.79 mg/l) while lower dissolved oxygen was found in well water (3.8 ± 1.08 mg/l) and borehole water ($.67 \pm 1.53$ mg/l). The mean transparency was higher in Lake Geriyo (33.33 ± 4.12 cm) compared to that of Upper River Benue (20.17 ± 3.27 cm). No transparency was recorded for groundwater. The borehole water had the highest mean electrical conductivity (668.33 ± 2.11 μm) and total dissolved solids (307.5 ± 2.64 ppm) while the Upper River Benue had the lowest mean electrical conductivity (71.5 ± 1051 μm) and total dissolved solids (39.17 ± 1.84 ppm). The highest mean biochemical oxygen demands were recorded in the Upper River Benue (4.32 ± 0.38 mg/l) while the well water and borehole had lower mean biochemical oxygen demand of 1.11 ± 0.21 mg/l and 1.89 ± 0.51 mg/l respectively. The mean ammonia level in Lake Geriyo, Upper River Benue, well water, and borehole water were 0.004 ± 0.01 mg/l, 0.003 ± 0.01 mg/l, 0.006 ± 0.02 mg/l and 0.002 ± 0.01 mg/l respectively.

Discussion

Several variations were observed in the physico-chemical parameters of the studied surface and ground waters. These variations may be associated with the mode of water usage and other environmental factors such as rainfall (Ayoade *et al.*, 2006). The temperature of the studied samples was relatively average because collection of samples were done at the peak of harmattan (January and February) and at the peak of hot weather (March). Similar mean temperature of 22°C to 28°C has been documented by Adedeji *et al.* (2019) from Lake Ribadu, Adamawa State. Moreover, water temperature values have been reported to change in response to changes in air temperature (Anago *et al.*, 2013). However, the parameter falls within the optimum range for fish production in the tropics (Bhatnagar and Pooja, 2013). The transparency from the study (33.33 ± 4.12 cm for Lake Geriyo and 20.17 ± 3.27 cm for Upper Benue River) are lower to the reports of Ani *et al.* (2016) who reported 49cm from the Ebonyi River and that of Adedeji *et al.* (2019) who reported 43.40cm from Lake Ribadu Adamawa State. The observed variations may be due to differences in sampling duration as Ani *et al.* (2016) and Adedeji *et al.* (2019) sampled for twelve months while sampling was done for only three months in this present study. However, the transparency values still fall within the recommended values of 30-45 by WHO.

The dissolution of oxygen in aquatic systems has shown a negative correlation with temperature; that is, as the temperature increases, the dissolution of oxygen decreases, and vice versa. The dissolved oxygen in the surface waters is higher than that in the ground waters, though it still falls within the recommended values of FEPA and NAFDAC but is lower than the recommended values of WHO. Other factors responsible for changes in dissolved oxygen include depth, wind, and the amount of biological activity that occurs in the system, such as degradation (Bature *et al.*, 2017). These factors can affect the amount of dissolved oxygen in the water. For example, as depth increases, the pressure on the water increases, which can result in a decrease in dissolved oxygen levels. Additionally, wind can cause turbulence on the water's surface, increasing the mixing of oxygen into the water and, therefore, increasing dissolved oxygen levels. Biological activity, such as the decomposition of organic matter, can also consume oxygen and lead to lower dissolved oxygen levels in the water.

The average values recorded for pH in both the surface and ground waters are optimum for fish productivity and this agreed with the report of Ani *et al.* (2016) and Agbaire (2015) and also within the national and international standards (SON, FEPA and WHO). This shows a balance between photosynthesis and respiration in both studied waters. The mean electrical

conductivity observed in this work is within the permissible limits of set standards (SON and FEPA) for domestic use and aquaculture. The total load of salts in water is directly related to its conductivity which in-turn is dependent on the ionic concentration and water temperature (Deline, 1992). Solomon *et al.* (2013) reported that high value of conductivity is an indication of water pollution and this is another justification that the sampled waters were not polluted. However, Sikoki and Veen, (2004) have reported that fishes differ in their ability to maintain osmotic pressure, therefore the optimum conductivity for fish production differ from one species to another.

Table 1: Mean values of physico-chemical parameters of surface and ground waters in Jimeta metropolis of Adamawa State

Parameters	Surface water		Ground water		International and National standards		
	Lake Geriyo	Upper River Benue	Well	Borehole	SON	FEPA	WHO
Temperature (°C)	29.67±1.57	27.12±2.11	30.83±1.63 ^a	28.83±1.73		26	40
pH	6.92±0.32 ^a	7.01±0.41 ^a	6.04±0.24 ^a	6.39±0.15 ^a	6.5 - 8.5	6.0 – 9.0	6.8
Dissolved Oxygen (mg/l)	4.23±1.32 ^b	6.27±1.79 ^a	3.8±1.08 ^b	3.67±1.53 ^b	> 4	> 4	> 6
Transparency (cm)	33.33±4.12	20.17±3.27					30 - 45
Electrical Conductivity (µm)	230.33±3.45 ^b	71.5±1051 ^c	200±2.28 ^b	668.33±2.11 ^a	1000	700	
Total dissolved solids (ppm)	107.5±2.23 ^b	39.17±1.84 ^d	83.12±1.68 ^c	307.5±2.64 ^a	500	500	1000
Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) (mg/l)	2.71±0.54 ^b	4.32±0.38 ^a	1.11±0.21 ^c	1.89±0.51 ^c		-	
Ammonia (mg/L)	0.004±0.01 ^a	0.003±0.01 ^a	0.006±0.02 ^a	0.002±0.01 ^a	>0.005	≥1.0	
Free carbondioxide (mg/l)	15.5±1.02 ^b	13.0±1.89 ^c	22.0±1.46 ^a	18.17±1.71 ^{ab}	10-22.5	10	

The total dissolved solids observed in this present study is higher than the reports of Oyem *et al.* (2014) and Ani *et al.* (2016) who both reported lower TDS from Groundwater in Boji-BojiAgbor/Owa Area of Delta State and selected Rivers in Ebonyi State respectively. The TDS of both the surface and ground waters in this present study are very far below the SON, FEPA and WHO recommended guideline value of 500 - 1000 mg/l. Water containing TDS of less than 1000 mg/l could be regarded as fresh water and good enough for both drinking, domestic and irrigational purposes as this would not affect the osmotic pressure of soil solution according to Shahidullah *et al.* (2000). However, extremely low concentration of TDS may be unacceptable because of its flat unexciting taste (WHO, 1996). Biological oxygen demand (BOD) observed in this study is similar to the report of Odoemelam *et al.* (2013) from Cross river at Afikpo in the north local Government area of Ebonyi

state, Nigeria. Though, this present study contradicts the work of Kdu *et al* (2015) who reported a very high BOD from Tsaeda agam river in mekelle city, Tigray, Ethiopia. The BOD is the amount of oxygen required by micro-organisms that are present in the water to break down decomposable organic matters into simpler substances. The greater the decomposable matter present, the greater the biological.

Conclusion

In conclusion, a critical look at the physico-chemical parameters of both the surface and ground water falls within the stipulated and accepted ranges of national (NAFDAC, FEPA) and international bodies. Hence, the water can be classified as good, stable and healthy for aquaculture purposes. However, there must be a constant monitoring of the physico-chemical parameters of both the surface and ground water in order to ensure that they are in good state all time for aquaculture and domestic usages.

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